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HR Practises in E-culture on the Basis of Qualitative Research in Virtual Organizations

Abstract: This paper aims to describe the HR practices that enhance e-culture. The research analysis, which was conducted based on empirical research, diagnoses and describes the HR practices that strengthen e-culture in virtual organizations. The data was acquired through 20 interviews with employees of the best IT companies in Poland (qualitative research). It describes the most common practices and tools used in the surveyed organizations. The paper contains some solutions and advice for HR specialists on how to accommodate organizational culture to a virtual organization's requirements. Since e-culture is still a relatively new phenomenon, it is not fully recognized. Thus, specifying the HR practices that enable e-culture provides insights and innovative managerial knowledge.

Key words: e-culture, virtual organization, HR practices, human capital management

Introduction

The changing economy has forced organizations to adjust to new circumstances. The three main reasons for these changes are globalisation, rapid growth in information and communication technology (ICT) usage, and economic crisis [Castells 2009, p. 336]. The mutual influence of these factors on the society and organizations gives rise to new social structures and new economic factors, thus leading to the evolution of organizations and the way they are managed. An exemplification of such an adjustment is virtual organizations [Grudzewski, Hejduk, Sankowska, Wańtuchovicz 2010, pp. 168–170]. This paper focuses on the human resource (HR) aspect of virtual organizations.

Organizational culture is regarded as a core factor that affects performance [Kotter 2001]. Many scholars have strived to validate empirically the effects of a culture on organizational functioning. It has been confirmed through practical studies that organizational culture affects organizational efficiency [Alvesson 2002, pp. 53–54; Xiaoming, Junchen 2012, pp. 28–37]. Furthermore, current research suggests that organizational culture allows a competitive advantage to be achieved [Dworzecki 2002, p. 288]. Moreover, empirical findings show that organizational culture has an effect on employee participation, commitment, and quality of work [Martin 1985]; it also affects financial aspects of the way an organization operates [Siehl Martin 2000, pp. 241–281]. Overall, current studies suggest that organizational culture has a significant impact on enterprises.

Organizational culture in a virtual organization is distinctive and unique. It has been described as the social dimension of virtual enterprise. It includes the necessary managerial tools to coordinate people's work in the e-economy. Thus, it provides some internal mechanisms that facilitate adaptation to changes [Kanter 2001]. The present paper focuses on specific HR practices in an e-culture.

The research was conducted on ICT enterprises functioning in Poland; this seems appropriate in this sector because it has been linked to virtual organizations. The operation of ICT companies is characterized by a particular style of management (e.g. project work, dispersed and changeable teams, lack of face-to-face interaction, electronic communication) which is associated with the concept of virtual organizations.

This paper aims to describe and analyse HR practices that strengthen e-culture in virtual organizations. Understanding successful HR methods in an e-culture can help to emphasise the main areas of interest during the shift from a traditional organization to a virtual one. Thus, the purpose of this research is to determine the most important HR practices that empower e-culture in IT organizations.

Virtual organization

The term 'virtual organization' emerged in the 1990s. It was introduced by A. Moshowitz [1986, pp. 335–404] to explain the consequences of extended usage of ICT. Subsequently, the concept was popularized by J. Byrne, R. Brant and O. Port, who defined a virtual organization as a "[...] temporary network of independent companies – suppliers, customers, even erstwhile rivals – linked by information technology to share skills, costs, and access to one another's markets. It will have neither central office nor organization chart" [1993, pp. 98–103]. Since then, the idea of this kind of phenomenon has received much attention amongst scholars. There are two main approaches to virtual organizations: structure- and process-oriented [Saabeel, Verduijn, Hagdorn, Kumar 2002, pp. 5–8]. The structural perspective focuses on the elements that comprise virtual organiza-

tions. It depicts enterprise as a system composed of various parts. On the other hand, the process approach concentrates on virtual organizations as ongoing functions. According to this view, virtual organizations constantly adjust to changeable environments [Jacobsen 2004, p. 12].

In analysing the contemporary definitions of virtual organizations, some researchers have stressed the network aspect and core competences [Bauer, Koeszegi, Wolkerstorfe 2003, pp. 26-46]. On the other hand, others have highlighted geographical dispersion and innovative output [Bultje, van Wijk 1998, p. 18; Jagers, Jansen, Steenbakkens 1998, p. 74; Travica 2005, pp. 45-68]. Virtual organizations might also be understood as a social network [Davenport, Daellenbach 2011, pp. 54-76] which can be depicted as a dynamic managerial tool based on ICT [Grudzewski, Hejduk 2002, p. 39; Perkowski 2009, p. 52; Scholz 2000, p. 371; Tapscott 1996, p. 10]. Another approach underlines the temporary cooperation between enterprises in order to exploit business opportunities [Kasper-Fuehrer, Ashkanasy 2001, pp. 236-237]. C. Lo, Y. Chang and K. Chung suggest that a virtual organization based on information management can achieve a competitive advantage [2012, p. 353]. The important factor is flexibility [Orman 2009, pp. 701-718].

Summarizing, the definition of a virtual organization includes ICT usage, geographical distortion, cooperation, flexibility, and core competences. Furthermore, this concept provides a description of a network of partners that adapts to changes in the external environment to provide innovative solutions and beat the competition.

E-culture

E-culture has been introduced to organizational science by R.M. Kanter [2001]. The idea of e-culture originated from the concept of a virtual organization. Since organizational culture is traditionally depicted as a pattern of common assumptions [Schein 2004, p. 17], it also has implications for the meaning of an e-culture. E-culture can be defined as a specific type of organizational culture, where underlying assumptions have been acquired and transferred through ICT tools. E-culture can be compared to a binder which creates a common interpretational dimension.

The empirical research on e-culture has identified seven factors characterizing e-culture:

1. Sense of community – involving trust, identification and knowledge sharing potential;
2. Strategic orientation – contains the mission, vision and organizational goals and their acknowledgement and acceptance,
3. Leadership – refers to creative and open leaders who encourage outside the box thinking and innovative problem solving;

4. Collaborative teamwork – describes members' commitment to teamwork, participation and patterns of cooperation;
5. Communication – covers channels and tools of communication in the organisation,
6. Adaptable structure of teams – refers to a changeable team structure and a flexible approach to work goals;
7. Direct relationships – describes the straightforward interactions within organizations [Bulińska-Stangrecka 2016, p. 16].

This characteristic suggests that HR practices should be oriented on strengthening cooperation, sense of community, task orientation and communication. It can be concluded that HR activities play a vital role in developing a e-culture

Method

The purpose of this paper is to study the HR practices that enhance e-culture. The central research question is: what HR practices contribute to facilitating transformation to e-culture? To evaluate the research topic a quantitative method has been chosen (interviews).

The qualitative method is a tool to broaden the analysed topics. The organisational culture is a largely multifaceted issue, for which qualitative methods are more advantageous in analysing its properties in a more comprehensive way. As e-culture is complex, the qualitative research is the necessary addition to quantitative analyses. [Schein 2004, p. 205].

To answer the central research question a few supporting research questions were formulated:

- RQ1. What is the role of HR Department?
- RQ2. How is the recruitment process conducted in a company?
- RQ3. Does the company organise any training courses for its employees?
- RQ4. How is the incentive scheme organized?
- RQ5. Does an organization involve any specific communication IT tools?

HR practices reflect the main aspects of HR management as well as facilitate the creation of specific climate¹. They shape organizational culture.

Table 1 illustrates the research questions and resulting variables that have been answered through the analysis of acquired data in this study.

¹ A climate refers to the perception of an organization. It is established on the basis of members' experiences. Whereas a culture is understood more as core values and assumptions. An organizational culture provides behavioural pattern that shapes organizational climate [Toulson, Smith 1994, p. 445.; Ekvall 1991, pp. 73–79; Ashkanasy, Wilderom, Peterson 2010, p. 4].

Table 1. Constructs of the research model

	Variable	Author / source
RQ1	employees support	M.M.S. Kats, I.J. H. Van Emmerik, J. Blenkinsopp, S. N. Khapova (2010), pp. 401–418
RQ2	Recruitment and selection	J. Stewart, V. Knowles (2000), pp. 21–38
RQ3	training and development	Y. Gong, K.S. Law, S. Chang and K.R. Xin, (2009), pp. 263–275
RQ4	Motivation and incentives	H.T.M. Bui, G. Liu, S. Footner (2016), pp. 1004–1023
RQ5	IT mediated communication	C. Gibbs, F. MacDonald, K. MacKay (2015), pp. 170–184

Source: own elaboration.

The main contribution of this study is to analyze HR practices in innovative organizations. Consequently, it provides a guidance on how to manage the social aspect of an enterprise that becomes virtual organization.

Research sample

In order to answer research questions a qualitative interview has been conducted on twenty members of IT organizations. The selection of a sample group for qualitative interviews was relevant. The interviews were conducted on a sample of twenty information technology (IT) organisations operating in Poland, representing companies characterized by virtualization. Of the surveyed IT companies operating in Poland, eleven were Polish companies (with Polish capital), and nine were the international ones (with foreign capital). All of the above companies used the high level of virtualization which was verified by means of a tool for measuring virtualization, described in the chapter on methodology of qualitative research.

The sample group distribution regarding sex was as follows: four women and sixteen men. Seven respondents were managerial staff, and thirteen of them were experts.

Organization of research

The qualitative interviews has been conducted by the author. Each interview has been recorded and transcribed. The interviewees have been assured about confidentiality.

Results: practices in human resources management in the e-culture on the basis of qualitative interviewing

The interview focused on practices in HR management in the e-culture in the surveyed companies.

RQ1. At first, the respondents were asked about the functions of HR Department in their companies. Among the surveyed companies, five of them did not have any HR Department. One company outsourced HR tasks to professional companies.

In the remaining fifteen companies, the HR Department was mainly responsible for personnel administration. Respondents from the companies, where duties of the HR Department were not only limited to personnel administration, mentioned tasks related to evaluation and assessment of the staff. On the basis of the conducted research, it was noticed that the HR Department role in the e-culture was related to recruitment, personnel integration and the support for personnel development and their self-assessment.

RQ2. The next question focused on recruitment process in the surveyed organisations.

According to six respondents, internal recruitment was conducted in their companies. The answers showed that external recruitment was preceded by the internal process.

Internal recruitment in the surveyed companies was helpful for retaining employees, and consequently developing the community spirit.

The organisations conducted the external recruitment by giving advertisements, on the basis of recommendations or through programmes for students. The referral system is connected with financial incentives in return for employing the recommended person. Head hunting was the final solution sought only when other sources of searching for employees failed. The surveyed companies also used ICT systems intended to recruit candidates. The recruitment process usually involved knowledge tests, work samples (displays of skills), mathematical and logical tasks. Knowledge of English language was also verified. The interviews were usually carried out by a superior and a co-worker. The HR Department was rarely involved in the interview, and as the respondents reported, it did not even have a decisive voice.

Thus, the selection during the recruitment process was based on competency criteria. Skills, knowledge, English language and adjustment to the team are the most significant criteria.

RQ3. The next question refers to trainings and development. It was intended to get information on types of training and selection criteria for participants. Only two companies did not organise any training courses. Financial aspects were decisive in one of those companies. Other respondents affirmed the organisation of training courses in their companies.

On the basis of the research, training courses can be divided into the following groups:

- technological,
- product-related,
- linguistic (mainly English language courses),
- developing social competences (soft skills such as social communication).

Technological courses referred to innovative solutions and “new technologies, which are not explained on the Internet as, e.g. they were developed by the company a month ago”. That demonstrated the innovative content of training courses in the e-culture.

Training courses in the surveyed e-cultures also supported knowledge exchange by the employees. E-culture in the surveyed organisations involved training courses which rewarded staff development and knowledge exchange. Sharing knowledge about innovative technologies was rewarded, and the workers by themselves initiated training courses and made decisions on participating in them. Training system was the structural tool for sharing knowledge and exchanging information.

The surveyed companies used ICT tools supporting the process of organising training courses. Eligibility criteria for courses usually included willingness to participate and volunteer application as well as the need for training caused by the use of specific technology or solutions for the performed project. Training courses were a kind of the company’s investment in its employees, and simultaneously were incentives for the personal development.

RQ4. The aim of the following question was to analyse the incentive mechanisms. Only two respondents stated there were no incentive systems in their companies. According to the answers, the remaining companies incorporated an incentive scheme. Financial incentive was the most popular in the surveyed companies. Incentives other than financial available in the analysed companies included: occasional gifts or refunding the purchase of notebooks or IT equipment.

Individual gratuities and bonuses usually depended on the achieved results.

Team motivation practices were also declared in the surveyed companies. The respondents described how the best team/department was selected. Team motivation caused a situation, in which: “even individual successes depend on the collective success”. Bonuses were paid for the result obtained by the whole team.

Innovation and creativity in the e-culture supported the incentive system. The surveyed companies strengthened their innovation and creativity by the sense of mission, development and self-fulfilment.

Incentive system characteristic for the e-culture in the surveyed companies was related with the ongoing improvement of technological knowledge, development, innovative approach and creativity. Cooperation played an important role as bonuses often depended on the team results.

RQ5. The final question referred to the type of technologies applied in the companies: All the respondents declared the use of IT technology in their companies. They applied tools for exchanging information, and the most common solution was SharePoint.

The interviewed people also worked using programming tools for code managing and supporting the process of programming. Communication technology was classified as another group. The most popular communication channels were Skype, Microsoft Link for teleconferences, own social networks, solutions provided by Google, such as Gmail, Intranet, Facebook, lifemeeting solutions or the company's community site. The respondents also used Cloud computing solutions. The company's community site was the solution for supporting integration of staff. Teleconference tools were also popular. Other mentioned methods were weblogs and microsites.

The function of technological tools in the e-culture was not only limited to merely professional aspects related to programming, project management or communication. Technological solutions were used in those e-cultures as the tools supporting work, enabling communication and involved in the creation of community spirit.

Research findings

Information obtained during the interviews showed that e-culture involves a multitude of personnel management practices. The fundamental areas of such practices were the recruitment and selection process, training courses, creation of confidence, incentives, actions improving engagement, and satisfaction.

As the main selection criterion, e-culture in the surveyed companies used content-related skills and, more precisely, technical knowledge. E-culture is the fundamental aspect that should be focused on when analysing virtual organisations. The recruitment process was mainly based on recommendations. It was not only a good method of attracting desirable candidates, but also helped to create a climate of friendship in organisations. The decision to employ candidates was made jointly by a superior and a member of the relevant team. This aspect suggested that employing a suitable person who matched the team was important.

The system of training in e-culture improves the process of knowledge exchange and supports innovations. The focus group from the surveyed organisations indicated the importance of internal training courses, which were structured in the form of a platform for sharing professional IT knowledge. It is important that knowledge sharing is often related to innovative solutions. The primacy of development and self-improvement is also reflected in the functioning of the training course systems in those organisations.

An atmosphere of trust is a required element of e-culture (dimension, community spirit). The analysed companies preferred improving integration between employees,

which increased mutual trust and the creation of relations by means of integration trips, programming contests or celebration of successes. At the same time, the team was an important element in creating a community. Thus, emphasis was given to developing a sense of belonging in groups (different ways of celebrating successes by individual teams).

Incentive schemes in the surveyed companies strengthened the efforts in individual development and improvement of content-related skills by means of individual bonuses. These schemes also supported cooperation by awarding individual premiums determined by team achievements and competition between teams.

Actions intended to improve personnel satisfaction were commonly performed in the surveyed companies. This suggests that taking care of staff is a very important element in e-culture: flexible working hours, provision of food and drink, investing in employee development, or openness towards their preferences regarding the nature of performed tasks. Such actions resulted in better satisfaction and engagement of personnel. The summary of HR practices applied in e-culture identified based on empirical research is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. HR management practice in e-culture

Research question	Variable	HR tools
RQ1	employees support	training, incentives, standards, flexible work time,
RQ2	Recruitment and selection	- internal sources, recommendations - knowledge tests, work samples (displays of skills), mathematical and logical tasks, foreign language - the interviews were carried out by a superior and a co-worker - adjustment to the team
RQ3	training and development	- training: technological, product-related, linguistic development, social competences - continuous development and self-improvement - knowledge sharing / internal
RQ4	Motivation and incentives	- mostly financial incentives - team bonuses - work efficiency was the basic criterion for promoting people
RQ5	IT mediated communication	- communication, social media,

Source: own elaboration based on empirical research.

The conducted interviews presented the actions undertaken by the surveyed IT companies in the scope of HR management. E-culture in the analysed companies is oriented towards individual mastery, which is related to a high level of content-related skills, cooperation in teams, knowledge sharing, work satisfaction, and staff engagement. The obtained results suggest a focus on innovation, retaining talented people, taking care of employee needs, and, at the same time, striving to make the most of employees' potential.

Conclusions: Hints for HR departments on implementing e-culture

The research goal in this paper has been achieved as it provides answers to the research questions. The data from the interviews is useful in developing practical advice for companies at the stage of implementing e-culture. These suggestions are particularly addressed to companies that plan to adopt solutions determining their virtuality. The effective management of a virtual company requires its culture to be adequately adjusted.

The research findings indicate that the reported HR practices enhance e-culture and consequently improve organizational performance.

Transformation of organisational culture towards e-culture may be achieved by implementing the described HR solutions that support particular dimensions of e-culture: community spirit, strategy-driven orientation, creative leadership, communication, team cooperation, smooth structure, and direct relationships.

Future research should explore HR practices in different sectors. It may also be interesting to compare HR solutions in different countries.

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